

Challenges of managing inflammatory bowel disease using biological therapies: a qualitative study from Iraq

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Abstract

In conflict-affected Iraq, managing inflammatory bowel disease using biologic therapies faces ongoing systemic challenges. Limited access to advanced diagnostic tools and a high prevalence of tuberculosis complicate the differentiation between Crohn's disease and intestinal tuberculosis, often leading to misdiagnoses and inappropriate treatments. This qualitative study explores the difficulties faced by gastroenterologists and internists in providing IBD care in resource-limited settings. Semi-structured interviews with ten specialists at the Gastroenterology and Hepatology Teaching Hospital in Baghdad identified key themes: diagnostic uncertainties, clinician skepticism about biosimilars, medication shortages, patient adherence issues, follow-up barriers, infrastructural limitations, and the need for systemic reforms. Delays in histopathological analysis and limited diagnostic capacity, coupled with high tuberculosis incidence, increase misdiagnoses and antibiotic resistance. The shortage of original biologics has resulted in reliance on anti-TNF agents, while newer therapies remain inaccessible. Establishing specialized IBD clinics, centralizing drug procurement, improving diagnostic capabilities, and adopting interdisciplinary management are vital steps toward sustainable care. Collaborative policy reforms and international cooperation are essential to ensure equitable IBD treatment in this conflict-affected, low-resource environment.

Keywords

inflammatory bowel diseases, biological therapy, qualitative research, patient adherence, Iraq

Introduction

Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), which includes Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis (UC), is a chronic, recurrent inflammatory condition of the gastrointestinal system that is increasingly prevalent worldwide. In the last thirty years, the incidence of IBD has escalated globally, impacting some 6.8 million people, particularly in regions with previously low prevalence,

including Asia, South America, and the Middle East (Ng et al. 2017; Kaplan and Windsor 2021). Recent epidemiological studies in the Arab world indicate a pooled yearly incidence of 2.33 and 1.46 per 100,000 individuals for ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease, respectively, with Kuwait and Saudi Arabia identified as hotspots (Mosli et al. 2021). In Iraq, it was reported that the prevalence of IBD was higher than expected, which is in line with previous studies conducted in the

region (Mahmood et al. 2023). This transformation is attributed to urbanization, alterations in diet, and shifts in gut microbiota, reflecting trends observed in Western countries over the 20th century (Ananthakrishnan et al. 2018; Jumaah Jebur et al. 2018).

Diagnosing IBD is a considerable problem, especially in areas where tuberculosis (TB) is prevalent. CD and intestinal TB exhibit similar clinical, endoscopic, and histological characteristics, such as granulomas, weight loss, and ileocecal involvement, resulting in frequent misdiagnosis (Choudhury et al. 2023). In Iraq, where the prevalence of TB is elevated (43 cases per 100,000), the differentiation of these illnesses is further hindered by the restricted availability of modern diagnostic tools (Mohammed et al. 2022).

The introduction of biologic treatments, including anti-tumor necrosis factor (anti-TNF) medications, in the treatment of IBD—which were previously reported to have significant efficacy in reducing disease symptoms and halting progression in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) (Mohammed et al. 2023)—has transformed the management of IBD by facilitating mucosal repair and decreasing hospitalization rates (Burger and Travis 2011). Nonetheless, their elevated expenses and infrastructural requirements restrict accessibility in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). Two studies conducted in Iraq have demonstrated that the cost of treatment is one of the most prominent burdens among patients with UC and CD (Abood et al. 2024a, b). Biosimilars, engineered to replicate reference biologics at lower costs, present a viable answer (Kay et al. 2020). In Iraq, inconsistent biosimilar procurement, stock shortages, and mandated non-medical switching exacerbate treatment continuity issues, frequently leading to relapses (Ben-Horin et al. 2015; Alatab et al. 2020).

Systemic obstacles intensify these difficulties. Disconnected healthcare infrastructure, limited specialized training, and insufficient patient education impede prompt diagnosis and follow-up (Alatab et al. 2020), in addition to the low availability of diagnostic tools such as fecal calprotectin and MRI enterography (Alatab et al. 2020; Banerjee et al. 2020). The increasing incidence of IBD concurrently adds excess stress to already overloaded healthcare facilities. Physicians indicate a threefold rise in IBD patients since 2000, with an increase in patient numbers not matched by proportional expansion in hospital capacity, leading to a deficiency in specialized outpatient clinics for IBD patients (Mosli et al. 2021).

Despite these difficulties, limited research has investigated IBD management in conflict-affected regions such as Iraq. Existing research predominantly focuses on Western populations (Ng et al. 2017). This disparity underscores the need for context-specific insights to inform policy and practice. This study aims to determine the difficulties encountered by Iraqi physicians in using biological agents in the management of IBD, in addition to other challenges related to diagnosis, accessibility, and follow-up procedures.

Methods

Study design and participants

This qualitative study employed a phenomenological approach to investigate the challenges faced by physicians in treating patients with IBD who are undergoing biological therapy. A clinical pharmacist and an MSc student researcher conducted semi-structured interviews. The sample size was established based on the data saturation point, a crucial factor in such studies. Data collection ceased when the saturation point was reached—when no novel information emerged, and new participants provided responses that had already been given. Participants were recruited using purposive convenience sampling from the Gastroenterology and Hepatology Teaching Hospital in Baghdad, Iraq.

Questionnaire validation

The questionnaire underwent content validation through expert review to ensure relevance, clarity, and coverage of key conceptual domains. Specifically, the items were reviewed and face-validated by a panel of eight experts from the Department of Clinical Pharmacy at the College of Pharmacy, University of Baghdad. Their feedback guided the refinement of item phrasing and structure to enhance comprehensibility and contextual appropriateness for the target population.

Inclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria were that physicians specialize in gastroenterology or internal medicine, possess a minimum of one year of experience prescribing biologics for IBD, and be willing to participate in the trial.

Data collection

Face-to-face interviews were conducted at the Gastroenterology and Hepatology Teaching Hospital in Baghdad, Iraq, located within Medical City. Each interview lasted between 20 and 30 minutes. A semi-structured interview guide—developed through literature review and expert consultation—focused on four themes: (1) diagnostic challenges, (2) barriers to biological therapy, (3) follow-up and monitoring difficulties, and (4) systemic healthcare constraints. The semi-structured interviews included open-ended questions, and written consent was obtained from interviewees prior to participation, with their information kept confidential. The full interview guide is provided in Suppl. material 1.

To ensure methodological rigor, the interviewer—a clinical pharmacist—received training in qualitative techniques. All participants were offered the interview guide in advance to familiarize themselves with the topics. Interviews were conducted in Arabic or English, depending

on participant preference. Arabic responses were translated into English by two bilingual researchers, with discrepancies resolved through a consensus process. Audio recordings, freely permitted, were transcribed verbatim and anonymized to ensure confidentiality.

Data saturation and sample size

The data saturation point refers to the point at which participant recruitment ceased, having continued until data saturation was achieved—defined as the point where three consecutive interviews yielded no new themes (Francis et al. 2010; Redaniel et al. 2015). In the present study, the saturation point was achieved at 10 participants; three additional interviews confirmed redundancy.

Data analysis

Thematic analysis was conducted using Braun and Clarke's six-phase framework. Braun and Clarke's method is a widely recognized and rigorous approach for identifying, analyzing, and reporting patterns (themes) within qualitative data. It offers flexibility while maintaining a clear structure for qualitative interpretation. The six phases include familiarization with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the report. This approach enables a systematic yet reflexive engagement with the data, ensuring that themes are grounded in participants' narratives while allowing the researcher to interpret meaning within context (Braun and Clarke 2006).

Transcripts were imported into Taguette for coding. Initial codes were generated inductively, followed by an iterative process of categorization into subthemes and overarching themes. Discrepancies were resolved through discussion. Emerging themes were reviewed with a senior researcher to minimize bias.

Ethical considerations

The study received approval from the Research Ethics Committee, College of Pharmacy, University of Baghdad (Approval No: REC06202478H; date: December 15, 2024). Written consent was obtained after the study's

purpose, voluntary nature, and confidentiality measures were explained. Participants were assured that declining to participate would not affect their employment status. No incentives were offered. All data were anonymized by removing identifying information from transcripts and substituting them with codes.

Results

Demographic information

Ten physicians working in the Gastroenterology and Hepatology Teaching Hospital in Medical City were invited to participate and were interviewed in the current study. The average age of study participants was 49.9 ± 10.5 years, with an age range from 38 to 60 years. The average duration of experience treating IBD was 11.76 ± 7.98 years, ranging from 3.5 to 23 years, as shown in Tables 1, 2.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the interviewed physicians.

Parameter	Value	
Age (years)	Range	38–60
	Mean \pm SD	49.9 ± 10.5
Sex	Male, n (%)	8 (80)
	Female, n (%)	2 (20)
Academic degree	Board	7(70)
	Board student	3 (30)
Specialty or field of practice	Gastroenterologist	8 (80)
	Internal medicine	2 (20)
Working experience (in years)	Range	3.5–23
	Mean \pm SD	11.76 ± 7.98

Study themes

The data obtained from the study interviews led to the identification of seven key themes that represent essential obstacles in managing IBD with biologic agents. These include diagnostic challenges, perceptions of biopharmaceutical therapies, an increase in patient numbers, infrastructure limitations, medication availability and shortages, patient adherence, follow-up challenges, and healthcare service improvements, as shown in Table 3.

Table 2. Detailed demographics of study participants.

Number of participants	Age	Sex	Academic degree	Specialty	Working experience
P1	60	Male	Board	Gastroenterologist	20 years
P2	57	Male	Board	Gastroenterologist	17 years
P3	45	Male	Board	Gastroenterologist	5 years
P4	59	Male	Board	Gastroenterologist	19 years
P5	35	Female	2 nd board	Internal medicine	1 year and 6 months
P6	55	Male	Board	Gastroenterologist	15 years
P7	38	Male	4 th board	Internal medicine	3 years and 6 months
P8	50	Male	Board	Gastroenterologist	10 years
P9	63	Female	Board	Gastroenterologist	23 years
P10	37	Male	4 th board	Internal medicine	3 years and 7 months

Table 3. Study themes.

Theme	Subtheme
Diagnostic challenges	Differentiation between Crohn's disease and tuberculosis Delayed diagnosis Limited diagnostic tools
Perceptions of biopharmaceutical therapies	Efficacy and safety of biosimilars Interchangeability and prescribing constraints
The increment in the patient numbers and infrastructure limitations	*
Medication availability and shortage	*
Patient adherence	*
Follow-up challenges	Limited access to essential laboratory tests and the unavailability of drug-level monitoring Endoscopy barriers Fragmented follow-up coordination
Healthcare service improvements	Specialized IBD care infrastructure Standardized data management systems

* These themes are presented without subthemes, as their content was sufficiently coherent and focused to be discussed holistically, without the need for further categorization.

Diagnostic challenges

Differentiation between Crohn's disease and tuberculosis

All physicians emphasized the significant diagnostic overlap between CD and TB, citing nearly identical clinical, endoscopic, and histopathological features. A gastroenterologist noted, "The overlap of symptoms in IBD and discrepancies in laboratory and endoscopic findings present a challenge in differentiating CD from TB" (Dr. F). This misunderstanding frequently resulted in misdiagnosis, with instances of TB mistakenly treated as CD and vice versa. Although PCR testing for TB was employed, it was considered unreliable in early-stage cases. "We face a challenge in distinguishing between CD and TB, and PCR sometimes helps, but we often do not feel confident in its diagnostic accuracy" (Dr. B). One physician described a case where "TB tested negative on PCR but was later confirmed via endoscopy" (Dr. L), underscoring the limitations of existing diagnostic tools and proving the unreliability of PCR in the differentiation between CD and TB.

In contrast, UC was consistently easier to diagnose due to distinct endoscopic markers, such as continuous inflammation. "Diagnosing UC does not pose the same challenges" (Dr. MO).

Most doctors believed that all the challenges faced in the diagnosis and differentiation are global and not confined to Iraq only. "This issue is a global concern, not just a problem we are facing," Dr. ES explained. Nevertheless, the diagnosis of Crohn's disease remains uncertain, particularly when ulcers caused by NSAIDs or atypical infections

mimic inflammatory bowel disease, resulting in misdiagnosis of Crohn's disease. "Small aphthous ulcers can be mislabeled as CD without excluding NSAID use" (Dr. MH).

Delayed diagnosis

Delayed diagnosis of IBD can result in prolonged patient suffering and complications, impacting the overall prognosis. Timely identification and intervention are crucial for improving long-term outcomes and mitigating adverse effects.

Delays in diagnosis may occur due to delays in referring patients to the gastroenterologist, as patients were reluctant to report their symptoms and feared invasive treatment procedures. "There can be delays in referring the patient to a gastroenterologist, or sometimes the patient may refuse to undergo endoscopy" (Dr. RA). Technical barriers, such as prolonged waiting periods for endoscopy, can lead to delays in providing health services. Another factor contributing to the delay is the insufficient interaction between physicians and patients, largely due to patients' fear of the diagnosis and its implications. "By the time a patient receives a colonoscopy, their condition may have worsened" (Dr. F).

Limited diagnostic tools

Essential diagnostic instruments, such as fecal calprotectin and MRI enterography, were mainly unavailable at the Gastroenterology and Hepatology Teaching Hospital in Medical City, Baghdad, Iraq. Patients often needed to undergo these tests abroad, which many could not afford. "We send patients abroad for fecal calprotectin. Still, most cannot afford it" (Dr. L). Another diagnostic test for CD is the anti-*Saccharomyces cerevisiae* antibody (ASCA), which is not consistently available. "The diagnostic tools, including anti-*Saccharomyces cerevisiae* antibody (ASCA) for Crohn's disease, are sometimes available and sometimes not" (Dr. EM). Histopathology reports, regarded as a diagnostic tool, are often delayed due to excessive workloads. As a result, they have been classified as non-definitive and not fully reliable. "The conclusion from histopathology is not definitive. It does not conclusively identify IBD, leaving the diagnosis unresolved" (Dr. EA).

Perceptions of biopharmaceutical therapies

Efficacy and safety of biosimilars

All the physicians considered biosimilars to be less effective than originator biologic medications based on observed clinical outcomes. "The efficacy must be lower with biosimilars compared to branded medications, and we have observed that the efficacy is indeed lower" (Dr. B). The physicians preferred original (brand originator) medications over biosimilars due to the robust research demonstrating their efficacy and safety. The variations in clinical outcomes emphasized their preference for original medications to guarantee effective patient therapy. "I prefer branded medications because their efficacy and safety are well-documented" (Dr. V). However, participants also considered it essential to conduct

additional clinical research to ascertain the precise causes of these discrepancies and to confirm that biosimilars are both effective and safe for use, as their opinions are based on observation rather than clinically measured biomarkers. *“The brand is better than the biosimilar, but the reasons are difficult to determine because comprehensive studies and patient samples are needed”* (Dr. EM).

Interchangeability and prescribing constraints

Stockouts of originator biologics led to a reliance on biosimilars. *“We use biosimilars only when originators are unavailable—not by choice”* (Dr. MO). All the stated that the unavailability of Humira (adalimumab) is the main reason for switching to Cinnora (adalimumab). The switching disrupted treatment continuity, with participants reporting that the risks of relapse after switching were often documented, with one gastroenterologist asserting, *“Most patients experience withdrawal symptoms (relapse of symptoms) when switching from the original drug to a biosimilar or between different biosimilars”* (Dr. RA). Consequently, a specialized physician recommended that biosimilars should be utilized primarily when the patient is in a stable condition to avoid relapse. *“Ideally, we should provide the branded medication and switch to the biosimilar once the patient becomes stable”* (Dr. B).

The increment in the patient numbers and infrastructure limitations

Medical professionals indicated that since 2000, the incidence of IBD has increased by a factor of approximately 3 to 4. *“In the early 2000s, we saw 1–2 IBD patients monthly. Now, it’s 1–2 weekly”* (Dr. B), which is considered normal by some: *“Even if there is an increase, it might be natural due to the growing population”* (Dr. L). Consequently, hospital capacities are being exhausted, as the infrastructure remains unchanged. *“As our population grows, so does the number of patients, but the number of beds has remained constant”* (Dr. MO). Furthermore, diagnostic tools have remained largely unchanged and have not expanded in response to the increasing number of patients. *“We have the same hospitals, the same endoscopes, and the same system”* (Dr. B), which could force patients to rely on the private sector for diagnosis.

Medication availability and shortages

The continuing absence of biological medicines has become a significant systemic issue in Iraq, interrupting treatment continuity, worsening disease progression, and forcing specialists to implement alternative (and frequently inadequate) strategies. Participants highlighted that these shortages impacted patient care, increased financial pressures, and imposed burdens on healthcare resources.

The limited availability of diverse biologic treatments presents considerable obstacles in identifying the most suitable therapy and delivering optimal patient care. The clinicians stated that limited access to advanced biologics

(e.g., vedolizumab) restricted treatment options. They reported that they are relying almost exclusively on anti-TNF agents (e.g., infliximab, adalimumab) due to systemic unavailability of alternatives. Dr. EM lamented, *“Our choices are limited to anti-TNFs—there’s no access to vedolizumab or natalizumab here.”* Frequent stockouts further destabilized care. Clinicians described recurring shortages of biologics, which forced abrupt switches to corticosteroids or immunosuppressants, such as azathioprine.

To mitigate shortages, clinicians proposed systemic improvements, including the involvement of the Ministry of Health in long-term procurement of biologics. *“Centralized procurement by the Ministry of Health, with bulk purchases covering 5-year needs”* (Dr. EA), while Dr. RA emphasized rationing: *“During shortages, reserve existing stock for current patients—don’t start new ones.”* Others advocated stricter eligibility criteria to prioritize high-risk cases. Dr. B emphasized collaborative care: *“Doctors, administrators, and policymakers must work as one team to ensure continuity.”*

Patient adherence

Clinicians indicated a typically high adherence to biological therapy, attributing this to patients’ need for symptom relief following the ineffectiveness of conventional treatments. *“More than 90% of patients adhere because they have no alternative—they’re suffering”* (Dr. EM). Other opinions linked adherence to poor responses to non-biological options: *“Patients are eager to improve, so adherence is very good”* (Dr. MO). Effective communication and education also played key roles in improving adherence. *“Explaining relapse risks enhances adherence”* (Dr. EA).

On the other hand, adherence was not reported in all cases. One of the clinicians stated that adherence is “fifty percent,” which was attributed to several causes. One such cause was the disappearance of symptoms, which encouraged patients to reduce or stop their medication: *“When patients feel better, they alter doses or stop treatment”* (Dr. B). Another observation attributed the decline in adherence over time to *“frustration from lost drug efficacy”* (Dr. MH). Nonadherence frequently resulted from insufficient symptom management or misunderstandings about the treatment requirements.

Follow-up challenges

The follow-up of patients’ needs requires collaboration and coordination of several factors, including laboratory results for biomarkers that assess disease severity, patient encouragement to undergo endoscopy, drug level monitoring, and clinician availability. A defect in any one of these factors may restrict optimal follow-up.

Limited access to essential laboratory tests and unavailability of drug-level monitoring

Essential monitoring tools, including fecal calprotectin, drug-level assays, and antibody testing, are either inaccessible or prohibitively expensive. Government laboratories encounter inconsistent availability, while private laborato-

ries are regarded as unreliable, according to one clinician: “We lack the availability of drug level assays and antibody tests, which are crucial for patient management” (Dr. L). This gap leads clinicians to rely on individual symptoms or basic testing (e.g., C-reactive protein), which compromises accurate monitoring. Dr. L emphasized, “Increasing doses blindly, unaware of drug levels, leads to haphazard management.”

The lack of therapeutic drug monitoring hinders the evaluation of biologic efficacy, leading to random changes in drug regimens without addressing resistance. Dr. RA explained, “We cycle through biologics blindly, lacking data to guide decisions.” Moreover, unavailable drug-level assays and antibody tests hinder dose optimization. “We increase doses blindly, unaware of drug levels” (Dr. L). The root cause of this issue is the high cost of these tests and limited availability in the public sector. “We do not conduct anti-drug antibody level tests because they are expensive” (Dr. EM).

Endoscopy barriers

One of the most important barriers to performing endoscopy for suspected patients is patient refusal, which is attributed to fear or discomfort, in addition to logistical challenges such as delays and poor preparation. All these factors hinder endoscopic monitoring. Endoscopic facilities are available; however, they operate under a workload exceeding their optimal capacity, which consequently compromises the quality of care. “Most patients refuse endoscopy, even when mucosal healing assessment is critical” (Dr. RA).

Fragmented follow-up coordination

Most of the physicians (eight doctors) state that patients often disengage from follow-up appointments after their symptoms improve: “When the patient feels well, they stop following up” (Dr. RA). These issues stem from the lack of doctor–patient contact after treatment, as Dr. EM pointed out: “Usually, the patient comes to take the treatment and leaves without seeing their doctor, like a gas station where you fill up and go” which is caused by the gap between treatment days and specialist availability. This gap is considered one of the factors that affect continuity.

Healthcare service improvements

Specialized IBD care infrastructure

Clinicians emphasized the necessity for specialized IBD clinics staffed with multidisciplinary teams and advanced endoscopic units to optimize care delivery. Proposals included the expansion of current gastroenterology facilities and the establishment of provincial IBD centers to provide regional access, similar to that provided for other critical illnesses. “IBD should be given the same level of attention and resources as other critical illnesses, such as cancer” (Dr. F).

Standardized data management systems

Doctors emphasized the need to establish an integrated and systematic strategy for the storage, follow-up, and evaluation of patient data. “The most important thing is to have

archiving, systematic processes, follow-up, and case evaluations based on their conditions, not on a subjective basis” (Dr. EM). This systematic approach would facilitate the identification of issues, the monitoring of patient development, and the assurance of efficient and precise treatment. “This would enable the doctor to monitor the condition, determine whether there is any improvement, and see if there is an increase in the number of patients” (Dr. B).

Discussion

The management of IBD in Iraq has systemic obstacles, which reflect greater healthcare disparities in LMICs, exacerbated by the nation’s prolonged instability (Daham et al. 2019; Abood et al. 2024a). This study highlights significant obstacles, including diagnostic uncertainties, biological deficiencies, disjointed follow-up systems, and infrastructure constraints, that collectively hinder the management of IBD. These findings align with global research while emphasizing context-specific concerns, including TB misdiagnosis and reliance on outdated medications. We understand the context of these difficulties, propose solutions, and advocate for prompt improvements.

One of the significant challenges that clinicians face is the diagnostic overlap between CD and intestinal TB, which has emerged as a central issue, consistent with studies in TB-endemic regions such as India and Pakistan (Makharia et al. 2010; Ma et al. 2016; Sharma et al. 2016; Choudhury et al. 2023). Participants exhibited nearly identical clinical and histological characteristics—a challenge worsened by Iraq’s restricted access to modern diagnostic tools such as interferon-gamma release assays. Misdiagnosis risks are heightened in Iraq, where TB prevalence remains high (43 cases per 100,000) (Mohammed et al. 2022), leading to delayed IBD treatment and inappropriate anti-TB regimens, which may exacerbate antimicrobial resistance (Makharia et al. 2010; Organization 2022).

The dependence on delayed or inconclusive histopathological results in Iraq seems to be comparable to that occurring in the Middle East region (Sharara et al. 2018; Alsakarneh et al. 2024). Fecal calprotectin and MRI enterography are considered standard tools for diagnosis in high-income countries (Harbord et al. 2017; Magro et al. 2017), which are not fully accessible in Iraqi public hospitals, forcing clinicians to rely on subjective symptom assessment. This finding aligns with Banerjee et al. (2020), who observed that in LMICs, restricted diagnostic tools delay IBD identification by 1–3 years. Participants recommend centralized laboratories with quality-controlled assays, consistent with WHO recommendations for LMICs (Stewardship 2016). Nevertheless, successful implementation necessitates international collaborations to address financing deficiencies.

Physician skepticism regarding biosimilars has been prevalent since the Ministry of Health in Iraq approved some biosimilar medicines that lacked EMA or FDA certi-

fications before 2020. Consequently, some physicians were initially against prescribing such biosimilars. A recent Iraqi survey found that physicians are concerned about biosimilar immunogenicity (78%), quality (93.2%), safety profile (95.1%), and efficacy profile (95.7%) (Mohammed and Kadhim 2021), and this perceived poorer efficacy mirrors worldwide patterns in LMICs (Smits et al. 2016; Kay et al. 2020). It was also reported that the majority of clinicians who enrolled in the previous study perceived that brand medicines are more effective and meet higher safety measures compared to their generic counterparts (Mahdi et al. 2020; Mohammed and Kadhim 2021).

Participants attributed relapses to non-medical switching between originators and biosimilars, a concern supported by studies demonstrating increased immunogenicity with frequent substitutions (Ben-Horin et al. 2015; Smits et al. 2016). This skepticism is exacerbated by Iraq's absence of therapeutic drug monitoring, which is essential for assessing biosimilar efficacy, as reported in previous research (Papamichael et al. 2019). However, the previous results, which reflect the opinion of clinicians, might be due to their unawareness of the new Iraqi Pharmacovigilance Centre regulations regarding the reporting of adverse drug reactions of biopharmaceutical medicines using their trade names. The Iraqi Pharmacovigilance Centre is responsible for post-marketing surveillance for all medicines in both the public and private sectors (Al-Jumaili et al. 2021a; Fahmi et al. 2022).

Stockouts of originator biologics necessitated reactive substitutions, compromising treatment continuity, which is also reported in other countries such as Lebanon and India (Assa et al. 2019; Banerjee et al. 2020). Clinicians' recommendations for standardized biosimilar procurement, emphasizing supply stability rather than cost, are consistent with WHO guidelines that promote stable formularies in LMICs (Kang et al. 2023). Biosimilar adoption in Iraq necessitates concurrent investments in physician education and therapeutic drug monitoring infrastructure, analogous to Rwanda's successful biosimilar implementation (Kang et al. 2023).

Persistent biological shortages indicate Iraq's disjointed supply chains and inadequately financed procurement mechanisms, which are attributed to the insufficient budget allocated to the State Company for Drug and Medical Appliances in Iraq. This is considered one of the main reasons for shortages in essential medicines in Iraq in the past few decades (Al-Jumaili et al. 2021a). Clinicians' need for anti-TNF drugs, stemming from shortages of vedolizumab and natalizumab, reflects the difficulties faced in several countries in Asia and Africa, where restricted therapeutic alternatives exacerbate reliance on older biologics (Banerjee et al. 2020; Watermeyer et al. 2023). Stockouts forced transitions to corticosteroids or surgery, increasing complications like steroid dependency—a pattern observed in conflict zones like Syria (Ozaras et al. 2016; Alatab et al. 2020).

The clinicians' strategies, such as centralized procurement and patient prioritization, reflect Rwanda's national registry approach, which enhanced drug availability via

bulk purchasing (Binagwaho et al. 2014). Nevertheless, Iraq's healthcare system, debilitated by years of conflict, lacks the governance structures necessary for implementing such improvements without external assistance. Promoting the inclusion of biosimilars in international subsidy programs may reduce expenses (Stevens and Huys 2017). Contingency stockpiles could prevent or reduce supply shocks (Angelis et al. 2023). These challenges indicate underlying structural issues, such as fragmented supply chains, underfunded procurement procedures, and inadequate contingency planning. Addressing these deficiencies necessitates the institutionalization of long-term forecasting, allocation of specific resources for biologics, and the establishment of national guidelines for managing medication shortages in IBD treatment.

Although institutional drug availability (e.g., hospital-provided biologics) facilitates adherence, difficulties remain in maintaining long-term involvement—especially for patients facing delayed relapses or financial obstacles to ongoing therapy. Elevated adherence rates, motivated by an urgent need for symptom alleviation, differ from those observed in high-income nations, where nonadherence frequently arises from complacency (Burger and Travis 2011; King et al. 2025). The dependence of Iraqi patients on hospital-provided biologics highlights the role of institutional support as an agent for compliance, similar to observations in Iran's public healthcare system (Karami et al. 2025). However, diminishing compliance over time, linked to dissatisfaction with reduced effectiveness, reflects global patterns in chronic disease management (Burger and Travis 2011; Pang et al. 2022). One of the clinicians who participated in the present study stated that a “fifty-fifty” adherence division among clinicians highlights unaddressed educational needs. Clinicians focus on communication, which corresponds with strategies shown to be beneficial in low- and middle-income countries, including culturally adapted counseling. Maintaining participation necessitates overcoming financial obstacles to follow-up care, such as travel expenses—a difficulty intensified by centralized biologic distribution (Feig et al. 2024).

The fragmented follow-up systems, characterized by inadequate laboratory access and patient apathy, highlight Iraq's deteriorating healthcare infrastructure. The lack of drug-level monitoring necessitates “blind” dose modifications, heightening the risks of subsequent failure—an issue exacerbated in environments devoid of therapeutic drug monitoring (Ben-Horin et al. 2015; Papamichael et al. 2019). Comparable limitations in Pakistan undermine IBD outcomes, as dependence solely on clinical symptoms results in inadequate management (Banerjee et al. 2020). Endoscopic barriers, including patient refusal and logistical delays, impede surveillance, as evidenced in Egypt and Jordan (Sharara et al. 2018; Alsakarne et al. 2024). Participants' requests for specialized IBD clinics reflect Turkey's multidisciplinary treatment paradigm, which has enhanced follow-up rates (Tozun et al. 2009; Yağız et al. 2022). Cost-effective

Figure 1. Graphical presentation of the study.

innovations such as telemedicine, well tested in India, might resolve deficiencies in Iraq's resource-constrained environment (Chellaiyan et al. 2019).

Participants' suggestions for specialized clinics and centralized data systems may help overcome the challenges encountered (Okoroafor and Christmalls 2023). Digital health platforms could modernize data management and address several challenges in the treatment of IBD (Abernethy et al. 2022). Collaboration among clinicians, administrators, and policymakers—as suggested by clinicians—is essential and significantly impacts effective health management. Rwanda's collaborative strategy for biologic procurement provides a model (Binagwaho et al. 2014), as does Jordan's collaboration with international IBD organizations to enhance diagnostic capabilities (Mazzawi et al. 2025). In Iraq, WHO-supported training programs, or "twinning" activities with regional centers, could expedite advancement (Hopkins et al. 2013), particularly given that a previous Iraqi survey of hospital healthcare providers identified three key factors influencing physician–pharmacist collaborative care: role specification, relationship initiation, and trustworthiness. These factors should be strongly emphasized to ensure effective cooperation among medical staff (Al-Jumaili et al. 2021b).

This research has limitations; the single-center approach may restrict generalizability, while the purposeful sampling method yielded varied opinions. Dependence on clinician explanations excludes patient perspectives, potentially overlooking cultural or economic barriers to adherence. Future research should incorporate patient interviews alongside quantitative indicators. Fig. 1 shows the graphical presentation of the study.

Conclusion

Managing IBD in Iraq necessitates addressing interconnected challenges, including diagnostic uncertainties, pharmacological deficiencies, and institutional inadequacies. The inequalities observed in LMICs highlight the need for immediate, context-specific interventions in Iraq's conflict-affected environment. Centralized procurement, diagnostic investments, and interdisciplinary clinics may help mitigate adverse outcomes; nonetheless, sustainable solutions require international cooperation. This study enhances clinician perspectives and offers a framework for equitable IBD care in resource-limited settings.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: The study received approval from the Research Ethical Committee, College of Pharmacy, University of Baghdad (Approval No: REC06202478H; date: 15 December 2024).

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Interview guide with physician

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Data type: docx

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